

Inner Metallic Complexes with Substituted Thiocarbamides

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Metal complexes of the type, $ML_n \cdot nH_2O$ (M = a bivalent metal ion, L = *N*-Benzoyl-*N'*-orthosubstituted phenyl thiocarbamide) have been synthesized and characterized. The coordination of thiocarbamides through their thiocarbonyl sulphur, carbonyl oxygen and nitrogen atoms was suggested from i.r. spectral data. The substituents chloro and methoxy groups are not involved in coordination. But the NO_2 group is coordinated to the metal ion through oxygen atom. The $Cu(II)$, $Ni(II)$, $Co(II)$ and $Mn(II)$ complexes exhibit normal magnetic moment at room temperature and possess octahedral stereochemistry as indicated from electronic spectra.

METAL complexes with different thioureas, such as *N,N'*-di(thiocarbamoyl) hydrazine¹, *N,N'*-ethylene bis(*N*-phenyl thiourea)², α -benzoyl- β -phenylthiocarbamide³ and *p, p'*-bis (thiocarbamoyl) benzene⁴ were reported by us earlier. As a part of our programme on the synthesis of metal complexes with different thioureas which are expected to be biologically important, we further report in this communication a few more metal chelates with *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-orthosubstituted thiocarbamides.

Experimental

The ligands *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-orthonitrophenyl thiocarbamide (BNPTC), *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-ortho-chlorophenyl thiocarbamide (BCPTC), *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-orthomethoxyphenyl thiocarbamide (BMPTC) were prepared according to the procedure as described in the preparation of α -benzoyl- β -phenyl thiocarbamide⁵. They were recrystallized from ethanol. The sodium salt of the ligands were prepared by adding calculated volume of standard sodium hydroxide solution to a weighed quantity of the ligand.

Preparation of the Complexes

An aqueous solution of the sodium salt of the appropriate ligand was added to aqueous solutions of metal(II) chloride (except lead) in the molar ratio 1:1. Complexes were immediately formed which were digested on a water bath for thirty minutes. They were then filtered, washed several times with water and finally with ethanol and dried in vacuum.

Analysis: The metal and sulphur content of these complexes were carried out by standard methods⁶⁻⁸. Nitrogen content was determined by semi-micro combustion process. The analytical results are recorded in Table 1.

Physical measurements: Infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 221 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

The magnetic susceptibility value of the metal complexes was measured using Guoy method. Mercury(II) tetrathiocyanato cobaltate(II), $Hg[Co(CNS)_4]$ was used as standard, and diamagnetic corrections were made using standard values⁹. Electronic spectra of the ligand and freshly prepared complexes were taken in dioxan.

Results and Discussion

The ligand in solution may exist either in thione or thiol form and can be represented in a variety of ways as shown in figure I, II, III and IV.

($X = NO_2, Cl, OMe$)

UV and IR spectrum of the ligand

The ligands are believed to exist in equilibrium with thione and thiol tautomeric forms. The electronic spectrum of the ligand shows an intense band at ~ 250 nm and a weak band at 210 nm. These features in UV region are characteristic of a conjugated compound and provide evidence in favour of the structural form II.

The i.r. spectrum does not show any band in the region $3400-3200$ cm^{-1} except a very weak band ~ 3040 cm^{-1} indicating the absence of stretching vibration of NH group. The weak band may be due to $\nu(CH)$ vibration of phenyl group. The i.r. spectra of thiols have been reported by several workers¹⁰. The (S-H) stretching vibration usually appears as a weak band in the region $2600-2500$

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE LIGANDS AND THEIR METAL CHELATES

Sl. No.	Formula of the Compounds	Colour	μ_{eff} in B.M. in $82^\circ \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$	Metal%		Sulphur%		Nitrogen%	
				Found	(Calcd.)	Found	(Calcd.)	Found	(Calcd.)
1.	H ₂ BNPTC	Greenish yellow	—	—	—	—	10.88 (10.67)	13.85 (14.00)	—
2.	H ₂ BMPTC	Deep cream	—	—	—	—	11.06 (11.19)	9.62 (9.97)	—
3.	H ₂ BOPTC	Yellow	—	—	—	—	11.82 (11.01)	9.85 (9.64)	—
4.	[Cu(BNPTC)H ₂ O]	Almirah green	1.76	16.83 (16.60)	—	—	7.94 (8.86)	10.63 (10.97)	—
5.	[Cu(BMPTC)H ₂ O]	Olive green	1.70	17.10 (17.28)	—	—	8.23 (8.70)	7.94 (7.62)	—
6.	[Cu(BOPTC)H ₂ O]	Olive green	1.73	17.75 (17.08)	—	—	8.96 (8.06)	7.64 (7.53)	—
7.	[Ni(BNPTC)H ₂ O]	Brown	3.00	15.52 (15.54)	—	—	8.58 (8.47)	11.23 (11.12)	—
8.	[Ni(BMPTC)H ₂ O]	Yellowish green	3.28	16.98 (17.02)	—	—	9.16 (9.28)	8.14 (8.12)	—
9.	[Ni(BOPTC)H ₂ O]	Greenish yellow	3.10	15.88 (15.99)	—	—	8.63 (8.71)	8.02 (7.62)	—
10.	[Co(BNPTC)H ₂ O]	Leaf green	5.2	15.48 (15.59)	—	—	8.62 (8.47)	11.54 (11.11)	—
11.	[Co(BMPTC)H ₂ O]	Faint green	5.1	16.72 (16.69)	—	—	9.34 (9.06)	7.92 (7.94)	—
12.	[Co(BOPTC)H ₂ O]	Green	4.8	16.16 (16.30)	—	—	8.28 (8.71)	7.83 (7.62)	—
13.	[Mn(BNPTC)H ₂ O]	Peach	5.86	14.77 (14.69)	—	—	8.55 (8.56)	10.94 (11.28)	—
14.	[Mn(BMPTC)H ₂ O]	Brown	5.94	15.23 (15.30)	—	—	8.31 (8.91)	7.66 (7.80)	—
15.	[Mn(BOPTC)H ₂ O]	Brown	5.85	15.04 (15.11)	—	—	8.56 (8.80)	7.76 (7.71)	—
16.	[Pd(BNPTC)H ₂ O]	Chocolate	Diamagnetic	24.49 (25.01)	—	—	7.37 (7.52)	9.73 (9.87)	—
17.	[Pd(BMPTC)H ₂ O]	Roofred	Diamagnetic	25.86 (25.92)	—	—	7.84 (7.79)	6.96 (6.92)	—
18.	[Pd(BOPTC)H ₂ O]	Terracotta	Diamagnetic	25.34 (25.64)	—	—	7.39 (7.72)	6.98 (6.75)	—
19.	[Zn(BNPTC)H ₂ O]	Yellow	—	17.14 (17.00)	—	—	8.19 (8.32)	11.07 (10.92)	—
20.	[Zn(BMPTC)]	White	—	18.30 (18.63)	—	—	8.88 (9.10)	7.84 (7.96)	—
21.	[Zn(BOPTC)]	White	—	18.75 (18.35)	—	—	9.10 (8.99)	7.51 (7.87)	—
22.	[Cd(BNPTC)0.5H ₂ O]	Canary yellow	—	26.19 (26.56)	—	—	7.74 (7.58)	9.83 (9.95)	—
23.	[Cd(BMPTC)]	Yellow	—	27.90 (28.21)	—	—	7.98 (8.03)	7.13 (7.02)	—
24.	[Cd(BOPTC)]	Yellowish white	—	28.06 (27.89)	—	—	8.78 (7.94)	7.04 (6.95)	—
25.	[Hg(BNPTC)]H ₂ O	Light yellow	—	38.56 (38.59)	—	—	6.18 (6.16)	7.94 (8.08)	—
26.	[Hg(BMPTC)]	White	—	41.34 (41.23)	—	—	6.43 (6.58)	5.78 (5.75)	—
27.	[Hg(BOPTC)]	White	—	40.39 (40.85)	—	—	6.95 (6.51)	5.58 (5.70)	—
28.	[Pb(BNPTC)]2H ₂ O	Grey	—	38.26 (38.07)	—	—	6.01 (5.88)	7.39 (7.72)	—
29.	[Pb(BMPTC)]	Deep brown	—	41.72 (42.01)	—	—	6.95 (6.49)	5.98 (5.68)	—
30.	[Pb(BOPTC)]	Grey	—	40.88 (41.63)	—	—	6.48 (6.43)	6.47 (5.63)	—

cm⁻¹ in thiols and sometimes also undetectable. However, in the present study no band is observed in the ligand spectrum in the $\nu(\text{S—H})$ region. The bands at ~ 1680 and 1520 cm⁻¹ arise due to C=O and C=N stretching vibrations respectively^{11,12}. The characteristic absorption region of (C=S) stretching are reported in the free thiocarbamide¹³ at 730, 1080, 1120 and 1400 cm⁻¹. The band at ~ 730 cm⁻¹ may be due to C=S stretching vibration. In nitro derivative the band observed ~ 1360 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to the $\nu(\text{C—NO}_2)$ vibration¹⁴ and the band ~ 690 cm⁻¹ in the case of chloro derivative may be due to C—Cl stretching vibration¹⁵. The symmetrical and asymmetrical stretching vibrations of (C—O—CH₃) group in the methoxy derivative were found in the spectra ~ 1030 and 1275 cm⁻¹ respectively¹⁶.

Spectra of the Complexes

The presence of water is reflected in the i.r. spectra of most of the complexes in the region 3600-3200 cm⁻¹. The width is due to hydrogen bonding and it seems to be coordinated to the metal ion. The strong band observed in the complexes ~ 750 cm⁻¹ which is absent in the ligand can be assigned to rocking mode of water. Coordination of thiocarbamides through their thiocarbonyl sulphur atoms result in the decrease in C=S stretching frequency and an increase in the C—N stretching frequency¹⁷⁻¹⁹. The band due to $\nu(\text{C=S})$ at 720 cm⁻¹ is shifted to 685 cm⁻¹. This shift suggests

the tendency of the metal through sulphur coordination. On the other hand, the C—N band undergoes a positive shift in the metal complexes and appears ~ 1590 cm⁻¹. The position of the band at 1680 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{C=O})$ vibration shifts to a lower frequency region in the metal complexes.

The NO₂ stretching frequency in aromatic nitro compounds with orthosubstituent is reported to appear in the range 1355-1345 cm⁻¹. When the substituent is a bulky one it approaches a maximum value of 1380 cm⁻¹. In the present case the band appearing at 1360 cm⁻¹ in the ligand can be attributed to C—NO₂ symmetric stretching frequency. This band undergoes a shifting towards the lower frequency region and appears in the range 1350-1330 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes suggesting the coordination of NO₂ group to the metal ion²⁰. Again the band observed in the ligand ~ 870 cm⁻¹ due to (ONO) bending frequency also affected in the metal complexes shift to 850 cm⁻¹. This indicates the NO₂ group links to the metal ion through oxygen atom²¹. However, in the spectra of metal complexes of chloro and methoxy derivatives, the (C—Cl) and (C—OMe) stretching frequencies respectively remain unaffected suggesting non-coordinating behaviour of chloro or methoxy group to the metal ion.

Considering the *trans* structure of the ligand would be more stable than the *cis*-form and in the light of IR results we propose for all the complexes to be coordination polymers with ligand links to

metal ions through nitrogen, sulphur, oxygen and oxygen atom of the nitro group. The insolubility of these complexes in water and other solvents points towards polymeric intermolecular linkage.

Electronic Spectra and Magnetic Properties

The copper complexes possess the magnetic moment 1.7-1.76 B.M. and its electronic spectrum shows a broad asymmetric band whose maxima lies $\sim 19,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ followed by another band near $25,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The former approximates to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in an approximately octahedral ligand field. The width and the asymmetry of this band suggests tetragonal distortion due to coordination to hetero atoms and also Jahn-Teller effect. The latter band arises due to charge transfer.

The visible absorption spectra of nickel(II) complexes shows ligand field spectral bands $\sim 15,000$ and $26,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The former band is weak and can be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow T_{1g}$ (P). The complexes possess normal magnetic moment observed for nickel(II) octahedral complexes:

In the present study the magnetic moment of cobalt(II) complexes are in the range 4.8-5.2 B.M. The electronic spectra show a band system in the region $16,000$ to $18,500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which possess the characteristic features of the electronic spectra of known octahedral complexes. The spectral transitions can be unambiguously interpreted to arise due to ligand field transitions of the octahedral component of cobalt(II) complex and may be assigned to ${}^4T_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(P)$ transition in an approximately octahedral field.

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